

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

A SYSTEM OF VISUALIZATION AIMED AT ENSURING THE UNITY OF PUPILS' ANALYTICAL AND HEURISTIC ACTIVITIES

Ibrahimov F.

*Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor
Shaki Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,
Azerbaijan*

Abdullayeva G.

*PhD in Philology, Associate Professor,
Shaki Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,
Azerbaijan*

Karimova S.

*Senior Lecturer,
Shaki Branch of Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The article refers to the "dialectical approach of system analysis" and considers the process of "regulating pupils' analytical and heuristic activities" as a subsystem of the "implementation of pupil-centered education" system. It is deemed appropriate to accept the unity of visualization and speech as one of its educational resources.

In this work, the unity of visualization and speech as a type of resource is kept in focus as a structural element of the subsystem "Regulating Pupils' Analytical and Heuristic Activities." It is logically considered consistent with the emergent nature of the system, as each part is a subsystem in itself and cannot carry functions that contradict the nature of the system it is part of.

The article presents the necessary parameters for determining the forms of unity (integration) of visualization and speech.

Keywords: whole, part, system, emergent property, educational resource, analytical and heuristic activity, action, communication, belonging, opportunity, interest.

Relevance of the Research Topic

Currently, in response to the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, the "identification of theoretical and technological foundations for the implementation of pupil-centered education" has emerged as a relevant issue. Among the cognitive problems that condition the solution to this issue, the problem of "determining the ways to regulate pupils' analytical and heuristic activities" holds a special place.

In order for the research object to be viewed as a system, the necessary requirements are met by the "process of implementing pupil-centered education," which is a system that includes the "process of regulating pupils' analytical and heuristic activities" as a subsystem.

The term "educational resources" is a structural element of this subsystem, and it has various types, one of which is the "unity of visualization and speech as a resource type." The selection of this resource type as a structural element of the "regulation of pupils' analytical and heuristic activities" subsystem, consistent with its emergent nature, and the adjustment of its necessary parameters for its dialectical unity with other structural elements in this system, plays a special role in solving the cognitive problem of "determining the ways to regulate pupils' analytical and heuristic activities."

Nevertheless, we argue for the relevance of the research on the topic of "The System of Visualization Aimed at Ensuring the Unity of Pupils' Analytical and Heuristic Activities."

Methodological Basis of the Research

In the research process, based on L.Bertalanffy's "System Analysis Idea" (*which is explained as the attempt to study the properties of an object based on the properties of its parts* - italics are ours - I.F., A.G., K.S.), the "System-Structure Approach," which has developed into an alternative level as an important branch of dialectics, as well as the empirical, empirical-theoretical, and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal connections of the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations have been used as the methodological foundation.

Interpretation of Generalizations Regarding the Research Materials

First, in order to clarify our position regarding the title of the article (the formulation of the research topic), we find it necessary to provide a brief comment.

We acknowledge that there may not be consensus in the views of researchers who intend to oppose the use of the term "directed system" by us; it is even possible that the phrase "directed system" may be interpreted as a "distortion" or "misrepresentation" in relation to the concept of "system." Therefore, it is necessary to justify the following: 1) The implementation of teaching and education is a system; 2) The requirement to ensure the "unity of visualization and speech" in teaching does not justify its evaluation at the "principle" level; 3) The "unity of visualization and speech" is a component of the system in which it is contained, and

it fulfills a specific function in the realization of the system's goal (regulating pupils' analytical and heuristic activities) in a manner adequate to the mentioned "association," in other words, it performs the mission of "possibilism."

As emphasized in scientific sources, a system is the unity of the interrelations of the elements that constitute it, and in terms of its logical scope, it belongs to a group of general concepts that can be applied to any object, event, or process. The relationship between "whole" and "system" is often explained in terms of "species-genus," sometimes used synonymously, and different aspects of the same object are noted. Sometimes, the whole is considered the peak of a system that is just beginning to form. [5;104-107] In our opinion, a part is a component of the system that is relatively independent; the whole is a system that encompasses parts that are interconnected and possesses certain properties that are not always present in the individual parts; a system is whole because it contains both its elements and the relationships between them; when the nature of the elements of the system is mentally separated, and attention is focused on the relationships between them, we encounter the concept of "structure" of the system.

For the research object to be considered as a system, it must meet the following requirements: 1) The object (whole) must consist of subsystems (parts); 2) The combination of subsystems into one system should contribute to the correct formulation of the problem (research goal); 3) There must be a property that defines the interrelationship between the subsystems in the system; 4) The system must be a part (subsystem) of a larger system. [9;8]

Despite the above, teaching is a complex system with interrelations between its elements. These relations include: the interaction between pupil and teacher activities in teaching; the interaction between teaching tasks; the relationship between the content and tasks of teaching; the connection between the teaching task and the pupil's learning capabilities; the link between teaching and the school environment; and the connection between teaching and the social environment, etc. The regularities of teaching are manifested in these interrelations and dependencies. [8;120-121]

Although teaching is an important characteristic of educational activity, it does not encompass all of its aspects. Teaching, in the broadest sense, refers to the acquisition of new knowledge, skills, and habits. However, acquisition and teaching activities are essentially different phenomena. Acquisition is an inseparable part of every activity area, not just the teaching process. Teaching activity, on the other hand, is a type of activity and a specific form of the individual's social activity. The concept of teaching activity (D.V. Elkonin, V.V. Davydov, and others) distinguishes the following components within the structure of teaching activity: 1) teaching situation (or tasks); 2) teaching operations; 3) control; 4) assessment. As can be seen, both teaching and the teaching process can be viewed as a system during research, organization, and management. [3;150]

The invariant dependencies of the teaching system determine its existence, as well as the regulation of the

dialectic between its parts in accordance with its emergent nature. These invariant dependencies are regularities. Observing and adhering to the fundamental requirements arising from these regularities in the organization and management of teaching is a logical approach, and these requirements are referred to as the principles of teaching.

There are many scientific considerations in the literature regarding the influence of the principles, which cover both the teacher's and the pupil's activities, on the content, methods, and organizational forms of teaching. This shows that the problem of teaching principles has been addressed by many specialists (Y.A. Komenski, I.H. Pestalozzi, A. Disterweg, K.D. Ushinsky, Y.N. Medinsky, B.P. Esipov, M.A. Danilov, I.T. Ogorodnikov, Y.K. Babansky, N.I. Boldyrev, G.I. Shukina, M.N. Skatkin, I.Y. Lerner, D.O. Lorkipanidze, M.M. Mehdizade, N.M. Kazimov, B.A. Ahmadov, A.Kh. Pashayev, F.A. Rustamov, and others). For detailed information, see: [1-8; 14].

In addition to including the principle of visualization among the principles of teaching, it was even considered the "golden rule" in pedagogy for a long time. Like many other teaching principles, the "discovery" of the principle of visualization was once one of the major successes in pedagogical thought. This principle, in certain socio-historical conditions, deeply influenced school practice and, in fact, became the very foundation of every teacher's pedagogical thinking.

Since the mid-20th century, the idea of applying visualization as a means to activate children's cognitive activities has been proposed. The well-established principle of visualization in pedagogy has served the purpose of organizing pupils' observation and ensuring more effective assimilation of new knowledge. Even K.D. Ushinsky (1824-1870), when discussing visualization in teaching, wrote that "visual teaching" is teaching that is not based on abstract concepts and words, but rather on concrete images directly perceived by the child (whether these images are formed under the guidance of the educator during the teaching process or initially through the child's independent observation). [12; 281-282]

The principle of visualization was not discovered experimentally, but empirically, and was closely related to the rules of classical sensualism. In their everyday experience, people believed more in what they saw than in what they heard. Teachers, too, relied on this truth in their own practice. As long as schools were fighting illiteracy, the effects of the principle of visualization were undoubtedly positive. However, when schools faced the challenges of scientific and technological progress, difficulties arose in the application of the visualization principle... Since the 1970s, psychological literature began to examine the principle of visualization from a critical perspective. [3; 86-87]

The principle of visualization relies on the power of sensory cognition; the importance of sensory cognition is not denied. However, psychologists are rightly interested in the heuristic possibilities of the principle of visualization: "Does the principle of visualization condition the formation of a particular type of thinking in pupils?"

Today, the principle of visualization is evaluated with new pedagogical thinking criteria. According to psychologists' firm belief, while the principle of visualization may seem attractive in itself, one aspect is undeniable: its practical application leads to heavy, "tragic" (V.V. Davydov) outcomes in terms of pupils' cognitive development. After all, the principle of visualization requires moving from the concrete to the abstract in teaching, not from the abstract to the concrete. This, at best, results in the formation of empirical thinking in pupils. [3; 87]

It is well known that in a learner-centered education system, the roles of teachers and pupils, who are at the center of the pedagogical process, change. Their activities are built based on predetermined outcomes. Along with integrated plans that align with the curriculum, the teacher prepares new technologies or selects the most suitable ones from existing ones. In determining these technologies, both the teacher and the pupil serve as the leading subjects of the teaching process. Relationships are established in a horizontal direction, following the "subject-subject" formula. At this time, pupils are the organizers of their own thinking, while teachers act as the organizers of the conditions for the pupils' development. The leadership role of teachers changes, and their activity in providing information becomes more limited. Instead, they transform into subjects who organize the pupils' independent cognitive activity and active creativity, coordinating and directing the learning process in the classroom.

In the proper organization of the pedagogical process, important didactic principles are referenced. In the organization of the pedagogical process in accordance with new curricula, the following principles are considered essential:

1. **Completeness of the pedagogical process** - The pedagogical process implements the goals of teaching in a complex manner (developmental, educational, and formative), encompassing the activities of both teachers and pupils that culminate in tangible outcomes.

2. **Creation of equal opportunities in education** - The same learning environment is provided for all pupils, and the pedagogical process is regulated considering their potential capabilities.

3. **Learner-centeredness** - The pupil is at the center of the pedagogical process. All teaching and educational work is aimed at meeting the pupils' interests and needs, developing their talents, abilities, and potential capabilities.

4. **Development orientation** - Pupils' cognitive activity is regulated, their achievements are analyzed, and the development level of their knowledge, skills, and habits is adjusted.

5. **Stimulating activity** - To ensure the effective and efficient organization of the pedagogical process, all progress in the pupils' activities is recognized and evaluated, increasing their interest in learning and ultimately guiding them towards more successful educational outcomes.

6. **Creation of a supportive environment** - The organization of the pedagogical process, based on an adequate material-technical base and a healthy moral-psychological environment, creates a favorable and safe learning condition that enhances quality and efficiency. [11; 281-282]

By the way, it should also be noted that, along with these principles, the determination of specific methodological principles in the teaching of individual subjects is considered to be of didactic importance.

As seen, among these principles, the "Principle of Visuality in Teaching" is not included. We appreciate this and strongly believe that the "integration of words and visuality" should be considered as a structural element within the system of teaching resources. It is possible to clearly see the dialectical interdependency relationships with other components in the methodological system of teaching a particular subject from the schematic description below, which is included in the system of resources (Figure 1).

In this diagram, the visual representation of the interrelationships between the components of the methodological system is reflected. The teacher designs the teaching process in terms of the formulated goal (the goal is the system-creating component, the "movement model"). The selected content of the teaching material, the development level, interests, teaching tools, psychological conditions, national mentality, etc., of all pupils and each one individually serve as the carrier of the teacher's well-thought-out activities, which, in a certain sense, holds the potential. These factors are participants in the creation of a new quality—the pupil's desired state of improvement. Undoubtedly, the person who can identify these potentials is the one who can design the teaching process.

The most important issue here is determining the place and form of the "reconciliation of the word and visibility" as a resource in the implementation process of education, just like other resources, and applying it in a way that will positively influence the efficiency of teaching.

An analysis of scientific sources clearly shows that this resource has not been used to its desired level. Let's look at some examples that may be sufficient to argue our point.

L.V. Zankov highly appreciates the necessity of combining the word and visibility and the importance of determining the form of this choice, mentioning the following four forms:

1. The teacher guides pupils in observing the object with the help of words, and they (the pupils) acquire knowledge about the appearance of the object themselves;

2. With the help of words (questions, notes, etc.), the teacher directs pupils to perceive and formalize the relationships in the "events (*the studied reality* - italics are ours)" based on the results of their visual observation and their existing knowledge, relationships that cannot be revealed through the perception process;

3. Pupils receive information about the appearance of the object from the teacher's words, and visual aids serve to confirm and clarify the teacher's verbal conclusions;

4. During the process of observing visual objects, the teacher himself provides pupils with information about the relationships between events that are not directly perceived by them, draws conclusions, and generalizes individual information. [16;116-117]

As seen, the variants of "reconciliation (integration) of word and visibility" presented by L.V. Zankov have been structured in accordance with the first two levels of education, and the stages of pupils' intellectual activity, specifically their analytical and heuristic types (logics), which we describe below, have not been followed: The structure of the analytical type of cognitive activity includes the following:

1. Understanding the difficulty and analyzing the problematic situation;

2. Identifying the main difficulty and formulating the problem;

3. Searching for a solution using a known solution algorithm or finding new analytical methods;

4. Solution and verification of correctness.

The structure of the heuristic type of cognitive activity differs fundamentally; at certain stages, it is similar to the analytical one, but it also has its own distinct features: 1. Understanding the difficulty and analyzing the problematic situation; 2. Identifying the main difficulty and formulating the problem; 3. a) Formulating hypotheses and developing them (creating new algorithms) or b) making hypotheses through sudden guesses and finding an intuitive solution; 4. Verifying the correctness of the hypotheses by applying the obtained solution in practice. [15;119]

The ideas regarding the use of the "Word-Visualization Unity Resource" (its "potential carrier functions") in the implementation of education are not lim-

ited to L.V. Zankov's presentation. Numerous considerations on the possible use of this resource in various forms can be found in scientific literature. As evidence of our point, we can refer to Q.I. Shukina's consideration of the "polysemy" of the cognitive load of word-visual unity in the teaching process, L.V. Zankov, N.A. Menchinskaya, and F.I. Yakovlev's views on the three functions of visualization (visualization as a source of knowledge, visualization as an illustration tool for confirming deductive conclusions, and visualization as the basis and cognitive support for sensory perception), M.I. Maksutov's addition of the fourth function - "formulation of the teaching problem, the means of creating a problematic situation," and E.Q. Mingazov's thoughts on the role of word-visual unity in activating pupils' teaching-cognitive activities. [5; 226]

E.Q. Mingazov concluded that visualization has an important "potential carrier function" within the teaching resources complex, and he divided it into two types and eight categories. He classified five types under the "visual imagery" category: natural, volumetric, descriptive, graphic, and conventional. Three types are included in the "non-imagery" visualization category: diagrams, tables, and formulas. E.Q. Mingazov arranges all types of visualization in a sequence according to their degree of abstraction. The zero degree of abstraction is assigned to natural visualization, while the highest degree of abstraction is associated with formulas and equations. According to him, pupils' activation progresses along a transition line from the concrete to the abstract, from general representation to individualization, from non-moving to moving, and so on. This transition occurs gradually with increasing difficulty in pupils' cognitive activities. There can also be a reverse transition. For example, the ease of solving cognitive problems and the confirmation of deductive conclusions reveal this very transition. [13; 413-415] Here, the auxiliary role of tools is implied: they have been used as illustrative materials to facilitate the acquisition of knowledge. The flaw in the systematization presented by E.Q. Mingazov is that he did not correctly identify the logical foundations of systematization, nor did he focus on the "*interest ↔ potential ↔ action ↔ process's involvement in the desired development, educational, and pedagogical level*" management vector.

V.P. Strezikozin divides visual aids into two groups based on their role in the teaching process: object-imagery visual aids and symbolic visual aids. The first group of visual aids helps the teacher use pupils' sensory perception to form concepts and ideas. In the second case, visual aids are necessary to convey the complex, interdependent relationships of the objects being studied and their internal structure. He points out that since the reflection of reality in human consciousness is realized in the unity of the sensory and the rational, it may not be practical to universalize the role and place of a particular type of visualization in teaching. It is necessary to reconcile object-imagery and symbolic types of visualization in the teaching process, and in any type of visualization, isomorphism and simplicity should be combined. [17; 153-155] V.P. Strezikozin also did not address the essential parameters that

should serve as the basis for determining and applying forms of teaching resources.

I.S. Yakimanskaya considers it appropriate to categorize visual aids used as teaching resources in schools into three types based on their content and function: 1) natural, material, 2) conventional and graphic representations, and 3) symbolic models. She also addresses the methodological issues related to the use of these visual aids in the process of knowledge acquisition. She emphasizes the necessity of selecting visual aids that align with the content of the knowledge, noting their significant role in the perception of teaching material. In her opinion, it is important to set sensory tasks for pupils at the moment of presenting visual material. The methods for working with visual aids activate perception, making it conscious and dynamic (without these methods, it is impossible to fully acquire knowledge). [18; 12-18] In I.S. Yakimanskaya's reflections, the theoretical and technological aspects of using visual aids as teaching resources have not been adequately clarified.

As it can be seen, in the presented examples, the considerations regarding the use of the "integration of visual aids with words" resource have not been presented in a systematic manner, and the necessary parameters for determining the forms of combining visual aids with words have not been shown. We consider it appropriate to include the following parameters in the list: the development direction of 21st-century Azerbaijani society and education; the "specificity function" (possibilities) in teaching; the expectation of dependencies corresponding to the methodological system of teaching; the focus on the management vector of teaching that leads to the desired level of development, education, and upbringing of the participant involved in the process ("*interest ↔ potential ↔ action ↔ process*"); the recognition of the teacher's activity as one of the project opportunities of the teaching process; the focus on the driving force of the realization of pupil possibilities; the reference to the characteristics of the teaching process when designing the movement of pupil possibilities; the acceptance of intellectual interest as a means for realizing pupil possibilities in teaching; the application of teaching methods as a form of intellectual movement toward new knowledge for pupils; the selection of processional movement forms of material corresponding to the pupil's zone of proximal development; the identification of directions of pupil possibilities after the problematic situation arises in the teaching process. In our subjective understanding, in order for the integration of visual aids with words to become a system aimed at regulating pupils' analytical and heuristic activities, the process (system) must be designed according to the presented parameters.

In order to fully realize the research objective set forth in the article, let us provide interpretations (scientific comments) of the above-presented parameters. This would positively influence the theoretical and technological merits of the research.

A teacher affirms their creativity when they have the capability to explore various actions. Clear pedagogical thinking emerges from their complex, uncertain ideas. In our opinion, referring to Lotfi Zadeh's idea,

which enables the modeling of human thoughts, finding methods in various forms, and implementing the decisions made, one can discuss the "specificity function." In the teaching process, determining what corresponds to the specificity functions essentially means uncovering the essence of this process.

The analysis of technologies that have found a certain degree of place in pedagogical practice shows that their structure includes the following elements: a conceptual basis for each pedagogical technology; the content of the teaching material; the organization, regulation, direction, and management character of the teaching process (or other means of education); the level of activity of the parties involved; the activity model, forms, and methods for pupils; the activity model, forms, and methods for the teacher; the evaluation of the results of the activity; the design of the process defined at the scientific-methodological level based on the system of goals and tools; the reliance on philosophical-methodological, pedagogical, psychological, social, and logical concepts; the adequacy of the content and the procedural aspect.

In our opinion, the success of any pedagogical technology should be evaluated based on the level of realization of pupils' potential and the achievement of new qualities. This is natural, as the transmission of human culture is based on the experience of *Конец формы*

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \{interests\} \\ \{potential\} \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{l} activity \\ communication \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{l} action \end{array} \right) \right\} \\ \rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} new\ quality \\ (personality) \end{array} \right\}$$

Here, it is worth highlighting the very relevant analysis by Professor Rovshan Mustafayev regarding the internal unity of potential, action, and personality. He rightly emphasizes that the concept of "potential" plays a special role in our thinking and is, to some extent, equal to our existence and daily life. Existence only becomes meaningful when it has the potential for action. Moreover, this is impossible without deep creative pursuits. Where there is potential, there is action. In turn, this creates a dialectical unity between particles and the whole. The idea that generates action is the vital being that shapes the new model of development. [10; 88]

When focusing on the dialectical relationship related to the teaching process (which is also true in the political context!), one cannot overlook the concept of "interest." It is undeniable that interest is always potential. It is interest that drives potential into action (Today, our world is also governed by interests!). Interest transforms through the inner world of the personality, and can gain value through its actions. The personality is always potential. Potential itself does not mean action. Without the idea that generates action, it is absurd to talk about new quality. By "idea," we refer to a thought that has reached a high degree of objectivity, completeness, and specificity, and is also practically directed towards implementation.

There are different types of potentials: general and individual, real (concrete) and formal (abstract). General potential reflects only the general aspects of objects and events, the preliminary conditions, and individual characteristics. General potential is conditioned by the

laws of development of reality, while individual potential is conditioned by the existence of these general laws and the specific conditions of action. Each individual potential is unique. If a potential reflects the significant, lawful development trend of an object or event, and there is a necessary condition in reality for its realization, it is called real potential. Formal potential reflects an objective, insignificant development trend, and there are no necessary conditions in reality for its realization. Formal potential differs from impossibility because it is something that cannot be realized under any circumstances. It should be noted that a large number of formal potentials do not transform into reality. It is also worth emphasizing that, due to some circumstance, a fully real potential can be lost or objectively remain unrealized. In such cases, it turns into formal potential. There is undoubtedly a relative difference between formal and real potentials. Potential arises in the existing reality and is realized, materialized in the new reality. As latent trends that express various directions in the development of an object, potentials characterize reality in terms of its future. In dialectics, it is accepted that development is not just about expanding the collection of available potentials but is a process of the constant emergence of potentials within the framework of reality and their transformation into new reality. In social development, the realization of potentials depends largely on their will, consciousness, and activity. The process of realizing potentials, transforming them into reality, becomes possible through activity and communication. In the teaching process—under the guidance of the teacher—special conditions are required for the constant emergence of the potential of the chosen object within the framework of reality and its transformation into new reality as part of the pupil's education, development, and upbringing process. These conditions should be capable of accelerating this process. [6 ; 16-18] *Начало формы* *Конец формы*

In our opinion, the "*interest ↔ potential ↔ action ↔ the desired level of development, education, and upbringing of the party involved in the process*" management vector is determined in the teaching process. The "choice" factor plays a particularly important role in this process. The regulation of algorithmic and heuristic types of activity (as a system containing optimal relationships) is related to choice. In teaching, it is "potentials," not "probabilities," that align with the function of belonging.

It is known from psychology that perception is directed toward a specific goal. Under the influence of a teaching task, the content and nature of perception change. The optimality of this or that description can only be realized when the functions of the given description are identified based on a thorough analysis of the structure and content of knowledge. [12; 262-264]

We are of the opinion that the following aspects hold special importance among the main requirements for the application of visual aids and the integration of visuality with words in teaching resources, as identified in teaching practice: a) The teaching process should not be overloaded with visual aids (the process should occur in a situation where pupils face challenges within

their capacity, and the educational process should precede development, serving a developmental function); "undesirable overload" reduces pupils' independence and activity in understanding and mastering the teaching material. In other words, an excessive number of visual aids (even if their integration with words has become a unified form!) hinders the mastery of knowledge; b) Visual aids should not create external associations in pupils; c) There should be a clear purpose for the use of the integration of visuality and words; d) The integration of visuality and words should be applied in accordance with the logic of the teaching process, regulating the dialectic between empirical and theoretical knowledge; e) When using visual aids combined with words, the age of the pupils must be taken into account; "In lower grades, only pictorial visual aids accompanied by words can be used" is an incorrect statement. It is essential to familiarize children with understanding relationships and dependencies through the use of conditional visual descriptions, and this conclusion is supported by our accumulated experience in teaching and research.

In summary of what has been stated above and based on the analysis of the accumulated experience materials, we conclude that the integration of visual aids with words and the sequence of their application should direct pupils' activities towards creating a model of the studied material. The nature of solving cognitive problems in teaching, as well as the pupil's cognitive activity itself, largely depends on the application of the types of visual aids that integrate with words (which we consider to be an appropriate approach to include among the types of teaching resources). This includes ensuring the integration of pupils' analytical and heuristic activities in the teaching process, as well as regulating these activity types, which is largely conditioned by the integration of visuality and words. Therefore, by utilizing the following functions of the integration of visuality and words, it is possible to regulate pupils' analytical and heuristic activities and improve the conditions for ensuring their optimal relationships: 1) by using it as a means of obtaining empirical data; 2) by using it as a means of applying deductive conclusions; 3) by using it as a means of reaching an inductive conclusion, generalization, and systematization; 4) by using it as a means of creating the conditions for transitioning from restorative activity to heuristic activity; 5) by using it as a means of providing an algorithmic description of analytical activity; 6) by using it to improve the illustration support of heuristic activity and to focus on modeling.

Scientific novelty of the research: 1) It has been highlighted that in the field of pedagogical science, the issue of developing the theory of pupil-centered education in response to the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution remains an unsolved problem. Among the issues directed at solving this, the determination of ways to regulate pupils' analytical and heuristic activities holds a special place; 2) Among the specific structural components of ways to regulate pupils' analytical and heuristic activities, the presence of teaching resources is emphasized, and the existence of different types of these resources, particularly the "integration of

visuality and words as a resource type," has been proposed; 3) The essential parameters for determining the "integration of visuality and words" as a resource in a system form have been outlined; 4) The functions of the integration of visuality and words directed at regulating pupils' analytical and heuristic activities have been identified.

Practical significance of the research

The scientific novelty of the research holds practical importance for both individuals conducting research in the field of pedagogy and those engaged in practical pedagogical activities, as it provides clarity of purpose.

Conclusion

1. In the "methodical system of the teaching process," teaching resources conditioned by goals and content have a specific place among the components of the system, carry functions in dialectical unity with other components, and influence the system's effectiveness; 2. The integration of visuality and words as one of the teaching resources is appropriate and takes various forms, with essential parameters for its formation in systematized form; 3. Efficient use of the functions of the integration of visuality and words can positively impact improving the conditions for regulating pupils' analytical and heuristic activities.

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